

HYPOTHESIS AND ITS PROOF

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Abstract: In the previous questions, the hypothesis that was always considered to be correct was checked. But in many cases it is difficult to state this correct hypothesis. It is necessary to build a hypothesis. For this, the values of n sequences 1, 2, 3, ... continue until enough material is collected.

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When solving a given problem, a general result is found from a specific result, depending on the observation of a person and according to his ability, that is, it is necessary to build a more or less reliable hypothesis. After that, the mathematical induction method is used to test this hypothesis. The method of mathematical induction creates an opportunity to search for general laws found in the hypothesis and removes falsehood and confirms the truth.

Issue 1. Let's assume

$$S_n = \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n(n+1)}$$

let it be Having studied S_n

$$S_n = \frac{n+1}{3n+1}$$

we say the hypothesis, i.e (1)

$$S_n = \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = \frac{n+1}{3n+1}, \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$$

Let's test this hypothesis.

Theorem 1. For $n = 1$, we have:

The left side of (2):

$$\frac{1}{1 \cdot (1+1)} = \frac{1}{2}$$

The right-hand side of (2):

$$\frac{1}{3 \cdot 1 + 1} = \frac{1}{2}$$

Theorem 1 is proved.

Theorem 2. Assume that formula (1) holds for $n = k$. Let's check if the equality holds for $n = k + 1$. We assume that formula (1) is correct in $n = k + 1$. Then we have:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{k+1} &= S_k + \frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = \frac{k+1}{3k+1} + \frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = \\ &= \frac{k^3 + 4k^2 + 8k + 3}{(k+1)(k+2)(3k+1)} = \frac{1}{(3k+1)} \cdot \frac{k^3 + 4k^2 + 8k + 3}{k^2 + 3k + 2} = \\ &= \frac{1}{(3k+1)} \cdot \left(k + 1 + \frac{3k+1}{k^2 + 3k + 2}\right) \neq \frac{k+1}{(3k+1)} \end{aligned}$$

As a result, a contradiction is created. This contradiction (1) of the formula shows that it is appropriate.

We will try to state the correct hypothesis. For this we calculate several S_n , in which

$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$, in:

$$S_1 = \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{1+1};$$

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3} = 1 - \frac{1}{3} = \frac{2}{3} = \frac{2}{2+1};$$

$$S_3 = \frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} + \frac{1}{3 \cdot 4} = 1 - \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{4} = 1 - \frac{1}{4} = \frac{3}{4} = \frac{3}{3+1};$$

Looking carefully at these equations, for arbitrary natural n

$$S_n = \frac{n}{n+1}$$

the hypothesis of equality can be stated. This is by the method of mathematical induction we check the hypothesis, that is, we check the following equality:

$$\frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot 3} + \dots + \frac{1}{n \cdot (n+1)} = \frac{n}{(n+1)}, \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (2)$$

Theorem 1. For $n = 1$, we have:

The left side of equation (1.1):

$$\frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} = \frac{1}{2}$$

is equal to;

(1.1) right part of equation:

$$\frac{1}{1 \cdot 2} = \frac{1}{2}$$

is equal to Theorem 1 is proved.

Theorem 2. If (1.1) is true for $n = k$. Then $n = k + 1$ is also true. Actually:

$$S_{k+1} = S_k + \frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = \frac{k}{k+1} + \frac{1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = \frac{k^2 + 2k + 1}{(k+1)(k+2)} = \frac{k+1}{k+2}.$$

It follows from Theorems 1 and 2 that (1.1) is valid.

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